

ARMS

Supercapacitors:
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Atomic Layer-coated Graphene Electrode-based Micro-flexible and Structural Supercapacitors

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Publishable Executive Summary

Deliverable 3.1 outlines the primary status of the metal oxide films deposited via atomic layer deposition (ALD) onto activated carbon as the positive and negative electrodes. The uniformity and conformity of the metal oxide films is ensured by extensively optimizing the precursor and process parameters. The metal oxide growth rate and film quality was evaluated through several material characterization techniques.

In relation to Task 3.1.a, three types of metal oxide (MO) films were explored for the positive electrode to enhance the specific capacitance of activated carbon. The MO1 nanofilm coated carbon electrode exhibited a 30% increase in specific capacitance of up to 128 F/g in a sodium chloride electrolyte. The MO3 coating produces an excellent specific capacitance of 123 F/g, a 56% increase compared to the bare carbon using a sodium sulfate electrolyte.

In relation to Task 3.1.b, MO4 was investigated as a negative electrode. The specific capacitance of the bare carbon electrode was improved by 18% at 90 F/g upon deposition of MO4.

Besides, compatibility with the graphitized activated carbon was demonstrated in Tasks 3.1.a and 3.1.b.

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List of abbreviations

AC = Activated carbon

ALD = Atomic layer deposition

SBR = Styrene-butadiene rubber latex

CMC = Sodium Carboxymethyl Cellulose

CV = Cyclic voltammetry

Ag/AgCl = Silver/Silver Chloride

C_s = Specific capacitance

SEM = Scanning electron microscopy

TEM = Tunneling electron microscopy

EDS = Energy dispersive spectroscopy

NaCl = Sodium Chloride

K_2HPO_4 = Potassium Phosphate

Na_2SO_4 = Sodium Sulfate

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Description of deliverable

1. Introduction

This deliverable closely revolves around the works related to Task 3.1, which aims to enhance the energy density and cycling stability of activated carbon (AC) electrodes through additional pseudocapacitance of ultra-thin metal oxide films deposited via atomic layer deposition (ALD). An optimized deposition process was established by extensive variation of the precursor pulsing times, while ensuring the uniformity and conformity of the metal oxide films. The number of ALD cycles was also examined to determine the optimal film thickness to maximize the additional pseudocapacitance without pore blocking and minimal increase in series resistance. In addition, a low temperature deposition process was explored to promote compatibility within a wide range of soft and flexible substrates that are typically thermally sensitive.

In Task 3.1.a, MO1 and MO2 films were considered as candidates for the decoration of the positive electrode. MO1 is a low-cost, abundant material that has excellent chemical stability. Moreover, nanostructured MO1 films present high-level charge storage abilities due to its shorter ion diffusion path. The MO2 was chosen based on its abundance in nature, low-cost, and minimal toxicity. In addition, the unique tunnel structure of MO2 facilitates efficient ion intercalations and leads to high energy storage mechanism through enhanced reversible redox reactions.

In Task 3.1.b, MO4 was also chosen as the decoration for the negative electrode. Aside from the interesting properties described earlier, MO4 shows great promise of enhanced electrochemical performance within the negative potential window due to reversible electrolyte ion intercalations by the transition of oxidation states.

2. Approach

A commercial AC (Kuraray YP-80F) powder was chosen to be the active material to be decorated with metal oxide film. The binder was a mixture of styrene-butadiene rubber latex (SBR) and sodium carboxymethyl cellulose (CMC), chosen for its excellent thermal stability of up to 288°C [8], an improvement over the initial binder studied. Figure 1 below shows a schematic of the general structure of the work done related to this deliverable. The graphite ink current collectors and the AC electrode were subsequently coated onto the substrates with the use of a doctor blade coater, then coated with the metal oxide using ALD. Afterwards, the bare and ALD-coated AC electrodes were assessed electrochemically with a three-electrode setup.

Figure 1. Schematic illustration of the work done related to this deliverable.

2.1. ALD process

The ALD process typically consists of two sequential chemical reactions to deposit the metal oxide films. These steps include the pulsing of metal1 (M1) precursor followed by water for the MO1 deposition, while pulsing of M2 precursor and water is needed for the M2 deposition. The M1 deposition process was optimized with a precursor pulse time of 450 ms for M1 precursor and 300 ms for H₂O with the expected growth rate of 0.4 Å per cycle. The MO2 deposition process was optimized with pulsing times of 3 s for M2 precursor and 2 s for H₂O with the expected growth rate of 1.1 Å per cycle.

In the case of the positive electrode, the MO1 deposition temperature was fixed for compatibility, and the number of ALD cycles was varied. The optimal balance between MO1 film thickness and increased electrochemical performance was observed at a specific ALD cycle. The sample was labeled as MO1 for the material and electrochemical characterizations. The MO2 deposition temperature was fixed with varying ALD cycles, and samples were labeled as MO2.1, MO2.2, and MO2.3, respectively. For MO3 nanolaminates, the samples were labeled as MO3.1, MO3.2, and MO3.3, respectively. For the negative electrode, the deposition temperature of MO4 was performed at varying deposition temperature, and the number of ALD cycles was varied, too. Samples were labeled as MO4.1, 4.2, 4.3, 5.1, 5.2, 5.3, and 6.1, 6.2, and 6.3.

2.2. Electrochemical characterization

Three-electrode cyclic voltammetry (CV) was chosen as the primary characterization method of the electrodes to provide an in-depth assessment of their electrochemical behavior. Silver/silver chloride (Ag/AgCl) was used as the reference electrode, a platinum coil as the counter electrode, and the AC electrodes were the working electrodes. In general, the potential window was varied to estimate the optimal operating voltage and was selected in the positive range for the positive electrode and in the negative range for the negative electrode. To fairly quantify and assess the energy storage capabilities of the electrodes with respect to their mass, the specific capacitance (C_s) values were compared and calculated using the following equation:

$$\text{Specific capacitance} = \frac{CV \text{ area}}{2 * \text{scan rate} * \text{mass} * \text{potential window}}$$

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Material characterization

No significant difference in the surface morphology of the MO1 coating compared to bare AC could be seen using scanning electron microscopy (SEM) analysis. Thus, the uniformity and conformity of the deposited MO1 film was investigated by high-resolution cross-sectional tunneling electron microscopy (TEM) images. The surface of the samples was prepared prior to the TEM imaging by depositing thin protective layers of carbon and platinum as shown on the bare AC sample in figure 2.a. Upon the coating of MO1 films, a dark uniform “hairline-thin” layer can be observed in figure 2.b and it can be estimated to be around 3-5 nm from figure 2.c. Energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDS) was also employed to determine its elemental composition and the maximum peak intensity was observed around the site of the MO1 layer as shown in figure 2c.

Figure 2. TEM images of (a) bare and (b) MO1-coated AC electrode. (c) TEM-EDS of MO1-coated AC electrode.

In the case of the MO₂-coated AC electrode after it has undergone electrochemical oxidation during the CV analysis, the presence of a “coral-like” nanostructures is observed as shown in figure 3b-d and 3f. Figure 3a shows the typical layered structure of graphite to illustrate the surface morphology of the Bare AC. The shape of the “coral-like” nanostructures appear to be dependent on the thickness of the deposited MO₂ film (dictated by number of ALD cycles), and transforms from spherical at 20 ALD cycles to long and sharp at 80 ALD cycles. During the CV analysis, some M₂ is stripped away from the bulk material and dissolves onto the electrolyte, similar to the studies reported at literature. Afterwards, the M₂ gets electrodeposited back to the AC surface and forms the “coral-like” nanostructures

Figure 3. SEM images of (a) bare AC, (b) MO₂.1, (c) MO₂.2, (d) MO₂.3, (e) MO₃.2, and (f) MO₃.3.

3.2. Electrochemical characterization

3.2.a Positive electrode

For the MO1-coated AC positive electrode, a simple electrolyte of 1:5 wt% sodium chloride (NaCl) in water was used for all of the electrochemical measurements, and the potential window was varied with upper limits of 0.8 V, 1.0 V, 1.2 V, and 1.4 V. The optimal potential window was determined to be 1.2 V because the undesirable Faradaic reactions which increase the serial-resistance were already observed at 1.4 V. A quasi-rectangular shapes of ELDC supercapacitors were observed for both the bare AC and MO1AC sample, even when the scan rate was increased as shown in figure 4a and 4b. The specific capacitance was calculated to be 99 F/g for the Bare AC and 128 F/g for MO1AC at a scan rate of 10 mV/s as shown in figure 4c. This improved energy storage capability was retained even at a high scan rate of 60 mV/s where the specific capacitance was calculated to be 47 F/g for the Bare AC and 60 F/g for the MO1AC.

Figure 4. The CV curves of (a) Bare and (b) MO1-coated AC electrode at varying scan rate. (c) The calculated specific capacitance values of Bare and MO1-coated AC electrode with respect to scan rate.

For the MO2-coated AC positive electrode, several aqueous electrolyte systems were tested, such as NaCl, potassium phosphate (K_2HPO_4), and sodium sulfate (Na_2SO_4). Among them, 1.0 M Na_2SO_4 electrolyte was chosen since it produced the best cycling stability and reversibility with the MO2 films, similar to the observations stated of the art. All of the MO2-coated AC electrodes produced CV curves with a quasi-rectangular shape within the optimized potential window of 0.0 V to 0.8 V, showing excellent electrochemical behavior. In figure 5a, the improvement in specific capacitance was similar between MO1AC and MO2AC. This is probably due to the dissolution of M2 where the remaining amount of MO2 layer even after being electrodeposited back are similar between the two samples. In the case of MO3AC, the specific capacitance is lower, probably because of blocking of the AC pores, which significantly decreases the surface area and available active sites. Thus, the thickness of the MO2 layer was considered to be already optimal at MO1AC cycles.

Figure 5. The CV curves of (a) MO2-coated AC and (b) MO3-coated AC with a Bare AC electrode at scan rate of 6 mV/s. (c) The calculated specific capacitance values of Bare AC, MO2.1, and MO3.2 electrodes with respect to scan rate.

In figure 5b, the enhanced electrochemical performance is observed to increase with the thickness of the MO3.3 layer. However, the lower specific capacitance of MO3.3AC compared to MO3.2AC, even though it has a thicker MO layer is probably due to the similar pore blocking as observed in the case of MO2.3 sample. Hence, the ALD process for MO3 was deemed optimal for the MO3.2AC sample which produced the highest specific capacitance.

The calculated specific capacitance values at varying scan rates for the Bare AC, MO2.1, and MO3.2 electrodes are shown in figure 5c. The highest specific capacitance was produced at a low scan rate of 1 mV/s where it was calculated to be 79 F/g, 102 F/g, 123 F/g for Bare AC, MO2.1AC, and MO3.2AC, respectively. This constitutes an impressive 56% improvement of the MO3.2 compared to the Bare AC electrode.

3.2.b. Negative electrode

For the MO4-coated AC negative electrode, a 1.0 M Na₂SO₄ electrolyte was also used for all of the electrochemical tests to ensure compatibility with the MO2-coated AC positive electrodes. The potential window was varied within the negative range and was found to be optimal from -1.0 V to 0.0 V. At a specific deposition temperature, the highest specific capacitance was observed for the electrode MO4.2, as shown in figure 6a. However, at increased deposition temperatures, the CV curves produced were similar to the bare AC and even lower for higher temperature as shown in figures 6b and 6c. This significant difference in their electrochemical performance is due to the effect of deposition temperature on the crystal structure of the resulting MO4 films.

Figure 6. (a-c) The CV curves of MO4-coated AC negative electrode at varying deposition temperature compared to the Bare AC at scan rate of 10 mV/s. (d) The calculated specific capacitance values of the MO4-coated AC negative electrode at different deposition temperatures with respect to the number of cycles (bare is represented as 0 cycles).

In a study reported in the literature, a similar combination of precursor M4 and H₂O precursor as used in this study often produces an amorphous matrix, and anatase crystal structure starts to form at a specific deposition temperature. In the literature, researchers produced pseudocapacitive electrodes based on amorphous MO₄ where its disordered and loose structure presents a considerable amount of free volume that may act as pathways for ion diffusion.

Thus, the amorphous nature of the MO₄ films deposited at our specific temperature could have more active sites for ion diffusion, thus contributing more to overall energy storage capabilities than those at higher temperatures. The calculated specific capacitance values at varying scan rates for each deposition temperature are shown in figure 6d. The highest specific capacitance achieved was 90 F/g for 40 ALD cycles at a deposition temperature of process 4 while the bare AC has a specific capacitance of 76 F/g.

The calculated specific capacitance of the positive and negative electrodes with various metal oxide coatings are summarized in Table 1 below.

Table 1. Summary of the specific capacitance values achieved by the electrodes.

	metal oxide	no. of ALD cycles	approx. film thickness	electrolyte	specific capacitance
positive electrode	bare AC	-	-	1:5 wt% NaCl:H ₂ O	99 F/g
	MO1	60	2.4 nm	1:5 wt% NaCl:H ₂ O	128 F/g
	bare AC	-	-	1.0 M Na ₂ SO ₄	79 F/g
	MO2	20	2.2 nm	1.0 M Na ₂ SO ₄	102 F/g
	MO3	40 and 5	4.4 and 0.2 nm	1.0 M Na ₂ SO ₄	123 F/g
negative electrode	bare AC	-	-	1.0 M Na ₂ SO ₄	76 F/g
	MO4	40	1.6 nm	1.0 M Na ₂ SO ₄	90 F/g

4. Conclusions

Activated carbon was decorated with three MO films to enhance the electrochemical performance of positive electrodes. The material characterization revealed uniform and conformal coatings of MO1 nanofilms with a thickness of 3-5 nm. The deposited MO2 and MO3 films showed “coral”-like nanostructures with varying formations, depending on the number of ALD cycles. Both results were achieved by optimizing the ALD process parameters, which enables the precise control of the metal oxide film thickness to maximize the amount of pseudocapacitive material while avoiding pore blockage.

In a simple aqueous NaCl electrolyte, the MO1-coated AC electrodes exhibited an increased specific capacitance of 128 F/g, a 30% improvement from the bare AC. The highest specific capacitance of the MO2 and MO3-coated AC electrodes was 123 F/g using a 1.0 M Na₂SO₄ electrolyte which is a 56% improvement compared to the bare AC. The electrochemical behavior of the MO4 coatings was also investigated when used as a negative electrode. The highest specific capacitance achieved by the MO4-coated AC negative electrode was 90 F/g.

5. Disclaimer

This work was funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Commission. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

6. Acknowledgements

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